

A STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF BRANDING ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF AJMI FOOD PRODUCTS

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Abstract

In the highly competitive landscape of consumer goods, branding is pivotal in shaping consumer perceptions, preferences, and purchasing decisions. This study explores the relationship between branding and consumer buying behavior, focusing on Ajmi Food Products, a significant player in the culinary market known for its quality, tradition, and innovation. Through a comprehensive examination of brand image, loyalty, awareness, and association, the research investigates how Ajmi's branding strategies influence consumer decisions.

This research contributes significantly to the fields of marketing, consumer behaviour, and branding, providing valuable insights for both practitioners and academics. The findings reveal significant correlations between brand perception and consumer purchasing decisions, highlighting the pivotal role of branding in shaping consumer preferences and fostering brand loyalty. Factors influencing brand selection include quality and brand reputation as primary determinants, followed by price competitiveness and promotional activities.

Keywords: Branding, Consumer Buying Behaviour, Consumer Purchasing Decisions, Ajmi Food Products

1. Introduction

In the bustling landscape of consumer goods, where choices abound and competition is fierce, the significance of branding cannot be overstated. Branding serves as the cornerstone upon which consumer perceptions, preferences, and purchasing decisions are built. Ajmi Food Products, a notable player in the culinary realm, stands as a testament to the power of branding in shaping consumer behaviour. This study sets out to explore the complex connection between branding and consumer purchasing decisions within the context of Ajmi Food Products.

This study seeks to navigate this ever-evolving terrain by unravelling the myriad dimensions of branding and its impact on consumer behaviour within the context of Ajmi Food Products. Through a blend of qualitative and quantitative methodologies, including surveys, interviews, and data analysis, we aim to delve deep into the minds of consumers, unravelling the underlying drivers and influencers that shape their purchasing decisions. At the core of inquiry, there are the fundamental components of branding: brand image, brand loyalty, brand awareness, and brand association. These pillars serve as the building blocks upon which consumers construct their perceptions of Ajmi Food Products. By scrutinizing these elements through the lens of consumer psychology and marketing theory, we aspire to unearth the subtle nuances that govern consumer behaviour in the realm of food products.

2. Literature Review

Punj and Stewart (1983) combine three research streams on consumer decision processes—task characteristics, individual differences, and elemental behavioural response analysis—within an interactionist model of consumer decision making. The study concludes that consumer decision making is best understood through an interactionist model that integrates task characteristics, individual differences, and elemental behavioural response analysis, stressing the importance of considering the interplay between these factors for a thorough understanding.

Hoyer and Brown's (1990) experiment underscore the importance of brand awareness in consumer decision-making. They find that brand awareness acts as a key heuristic, simplifying decisions for familiar consumers but potentially leading to overlooked quality differences. The study concludes that advertising effectively boosts brand-choice probabilities by enhancing brand awareness, which simplifies decision-making for those already aware of the brand.

Keller (1993) presents a framework for customer-based brand equity, defined as the impact of brand knowledge on consumer reactions to marketing. Positive brand equity arises when consumers respond more favourably to well-known brands. This study is driven by strong, positive, and distinctive brand associations in memory, resulting in better consumer responses to marketing for established brands compared to lesser-known ones.

Loken and John (1993) examine how brand extensions may dilute family brand beliefs. Their experiments show that dilution occurs when extension attributes conflict with family brand beliefs, but this diminishes if the extension is seen as atypical. The findings apply across various categories and support alternative theories, including "bookkeeping" and "typicality-based" models, depending on belief assessment.

Dick and Basu (1994) define customer loyalty as the strength of the link between relative attitude and repeat patronage, mediated by social norms and situational factors. They highlight cognitive, affective, and conative antecedents as key influencers of relative attitude. The study concludes that loyalty depends on this robust relationship, shaped by various motivational, perceptual, and behavioural consequences.

Aaker (1996) examines brand strength, noting that brands like Kodak, American Express, and IBM are robust due to consistent quality, clear positioning, and strong market presence. He stresses that brand strength fluctuates with consumer perception and competition. Measuring brand equity beyond immediate products offers insights for managing diverse portfolios and benchmarking against top performers.

Srivastava, Shervani, and Fahey (1998) link marketing to finance through market-based assets like customer and channel relationships, vital for enhancing shareholder value via improved cash flow stability and growth. This study states that effective branding enhances consumer perceptions, reduces purchase risk, and fosters long-term relationships, driving stable revenue streams and increasing brand value.

Verlegh and Steenkamp (1999) analyse country-of-origin effects on consumer behaviour through a narrative review and quantitative meta-analysis. They find that country-of-origin significantly impacts perceived quality, attitudes, and purchase intentions across cognitive, affective, and normative dimensions, concluding that it notably influences product evaluations.

Krishnan and Chakravarti (1999) propose a conceptual framework for understanding memory test performance and suggest a diagnostic template for evaluating advertisements. They review direct and indirect memory tests, exploring how these tests capture ad exposure memory traces. The study identifies factors affecting performance, including stimulus relevance, processing depth, retrieval cues, and individual differences.

Chandon, Wansink, and Laurent (2000) examine sales promotions' benefits beyond monetary savings, identifying three hedonic (value expression, entertainment, exploration) and three utilitarian (savings, higher quality, convenience) benefits. Their framework shows promotion effectiveness depends on benefit-product type alignment. This study finds that high-equity brands benefit more from monetary promotions for utilitarian products, highlighting the importance of aligning promotional benefits with product types.

3. Objectives

- To analyze the influence of branding on consumer buying behavior of Ajmi food products.
- To evaluate the impact of Ajmi's brand perception on consumer purchasing decisions.
- To analyze the factors that influence in brand selection.
- To find out the customers satisfaction level of Ajmi food products.

4. Research Methodology

The information for this study was collected freshly and thus it was original in character, it was collected through a questionnaire. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents through Google form.

4.1 Research Design

This study has incorporated the descriptive research design. It involves a quantitative approach with a sample size of 100 respondents. It includes surveys to collect data on demographics, branding perceptions, purchasing behaviour, and satisfaction levels related to Ajmi Food Products.

4.2 Sample Design

100 respondents are chosen so that it could give a fair response to achieve the objectives. Convenience sampling technique has been used.

4.3 Data Sources

Primary Data: Primary data was gathered through a structured questionnaire administered to 100 respondents. This method allowed for direct insights into consumer perceptions, preferences, and behaviours related to Ajmi Food Products.

Secondary Data: Secondary data sources included academic journals, articles, and online reviews retrieved from databases and relevant online platforms. These sources provided theoretical frameworks, previous research findings, and industry insights related to branding, consumer behaviour, and food product marketing.

5. Data Analysis

5.1 Frequency Analysis

Overall customers satisfaction level of Ajmi food products.

Table 5.1.1: Table showing the frequency distribution of the overall customer satisfaction level

Overall Satisfaction					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	6	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Neutral	11	11.0	11.0	17.0
	Agree	54	54.0	54.0	71.0
	Strongly Agree	29	29.0	29.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.1.1: Figure showing the frequency distribution of the overall customer satisfaction level

Interpretation

The survey on overall satisfaction reveals that a majority of respondents are satisfied, with 54% agreeing and 29% strongly agreeing, totalling 83% positive responses. In contrast, 11% of respondents are neutral, and 6% disagree, indicating a generally high level of satisfaction among the participants.

5.2 Weighted Sum Analysis

Analysis of the influence of branding on consumer buying behavior of Ajmi food products.

Table 5.2.1: Table showing the weighted sum analysis of factors influencing consumer buying behaviour of Ajmi food products

5-Strongly Agree, 4-Agree, 3-Neutral, 2-Disagree, 1-Strongly Disagree

zSl. No.	Attributes	5	4	3	2	Total	Weighted Sum	Rank
1	Price	31	42	24	3	100	401	2
2	Product Quality	40	32	26	2	100	410	1
3	Product Availability	25	36	28	11	100	375	3
4	Product Range	15	26	44	15	100	341	6
5	Packaging	17	28	39	16	100	346	4
6	Promotions	16	22	42	20	100	334	7
7	Social Influence	19	26	33	22	100	342	5

Interpretation

This weighted analysis evaluates seven product attributes, assigning scores from 5 (highest) to 2 (lowest), and reveals their relative importance and customer satisfaction. Product Quality is the highest ranked attribute with a weighted sum of 410, indicating its critical importance to customers. Following closely are Price (401), Product Availability (375) and reflecting their significant roles in customer satisfaction. Mid-ranked attributes include Packaging (346) and Social Influence (342), which show moderate importance and potential for enhancement. Product Range (341) and Promotions (334) are the lowest ranked, suggesting they are less influential in customer satisfaction but still present opportunities for improvement. This analysis underscores the need to maintain high standards in Product Quality and Availability while also focusing on improving Packaging, Social Influence, Product Range, and Promotions to enhance overall customer satisfaction and product appeal.

5.3 Chi-Square Test

Evaluation of the impact of Ajmi's brand perception on consumer purchasing decisions.

5.3.1 Chi-Square Test -Product Purchase Decision * Perceived Value

H0: There is no significant relationship between product purchase decision and perceived value

H1: There is significant relationship between product purchase decision and perceived value

Table 5.3.1: Table showing the relationship between Product Purchase Decision and Perceived value

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	132.107 ^a	9	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	130.105	9	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	65.989	1	<.001
N of Valid Cases	100		
a. 8 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .20.			

Interpretation

From the above table p value <0.001 so we reject H0. Therefore, there is significant relationship between product purchase decision and perceived value.

5.3.2 Chi-Square Test -Product Purchase Decision * Brand Image

H0: There is no significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand image

H1: There is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand image

Table 5.3.2: Table showing the relationship between Product Purchase Decision and Brand Image

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	135.172 ^a	9	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	114.100	9	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	69.212	1	<.001
N of Valid Cases	100		
a. 11 cells (68.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .40.			

Interpretation

From the above table p value <0.001, so we reject H0. Therefore, there is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand image.

5.3.3 Chi-Square Test -Product Purchase Decision * Brand Reliability

H0: There is no significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand reliability.

H1: There is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand reliability.

Table 5.3.3: Table showing the relationship between Product Purchase Decision and Brand Reliability

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	159.404 ^a	9	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	161.205	9	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	74.573	1	<.001
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 9 cells (56.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.60.

Interpretation

From the above table p value <0.001, so we reject H0. Therefore, there is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand reliability.

5.3.4 Chi-Square Test -Product Purchase Decision * Brand Popularity

H0: There is no significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand popularity.

H1: There is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand popularity.

Table 5.3.4: Table showing the relationship between Product Purchase Decision and Brand Popularity

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	129.176 ^a	6	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	105.963	6	<.001

Linear-by-Linear Association	64.024	1	<.001
N of Valid Cases	100		
a. 5 cells (41.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .90.			

Interpretation

From the above table p value <0.001, so we reject H0. Therefore, there is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand popularity.

5.3.5 Chi-Square Test -Product Purchase Decision * Brand Recommendations

H0: There is no significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand recommendations.

H1: There is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand recommendations.

Table 5.3.5: Table showing the relationship between Product Purchase Decision and Brand Recommendations

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	113.632 ^a	9	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	119.607	9	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	52.643	1	<.001
N of Valid Cases	100		
a. 10 cells (62.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .40.			

Interpretation

From the above table p value <0.001, so we reject H0. Therefore, there is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand recommendations.

5.3.6 Chi-Square Test -Product Purchase Decision * Brand Uniqueness

H0: There is no significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand uniqueness.

H1: There is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand uniqueness.

Table 5.3.6: Table showing the relationship between Product Purchase Decision and Brand Uniqueness

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	127.866 ^a	9	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	110.742	9	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	68.187	1	<.001
N of Valid Cases	100		
a. 9 cells (56.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .20.			

Interpretation

From the above table p value <0.001, so we reject H0. Therefore, there is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand uniqueness.

5.3.7 Chi-Square Test -Product Purchase Decision * Brand Transparency

H0: There is no significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand transparency.

H1: There is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand transparency.

Table 5.3.7: Table showing the relationship between Product Purchase Decision and Brand Transparency

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	137.192 ^a	9	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	137.457	9	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	70.101	1	<.001
N of Valid Cases	100		
a. 9 cells (56.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.10.			

Interpretation

From the above table p value <0.001 , so we reject H_0 . Therefore, there is significant relationship between product purchase decision and brand transparency.

6. Findings

- Majority of respondents (70%) for Ajmi Food Products are aged between 21-50, with a significant segment (36%) falling within 21-35 years.
- A substantial female majority (69%) exists among consumers of Ajmi Food Products, with a balanced marital status (50% married, 50% unmarried).
- Employed individuals constitute 41% of Ajmi Food Products consumers, followed by 22% students and 27% unemployed.
- Monthly income distribution reveals 41% earning 30,001-40,000, while 14% earn below 20,000, and 16% earn above 40,000.
- Product usage duration shows 44% have used Ajmi Food Products for 2-3 years, and 7% for less than a year.
- Significant associations found between Ajmi's brand perception and purchasing decisions highlight the influence of perceived value, image, popularity, and recommendations.
- Strong correlations exist between brand recommendations and product purchases, as well as originality and transparency influencing consumer preferences for Ajmi products.
- Brand Quality ranks highest (weighted sum 424), followed by Brand Recognition (417), Advertising Impact (366), and Brand Trust (352) among Ajmi Food Products consumers.
- Factor analysis confirms all brand attributes significantly load onto a cohesive factor, indicating their collective influence on consumer behaviour.
- High overall customer satisfaction (83%) with Ajmi Food Products underscores positive responses, particularly regarding quality and taste, while suggesting opportunities for improvement in availability and variety.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the substantial impact of branding on consumer purchasing behaviour, with a specific focus on Ajmi food products. By delving into various theoretical frameworks and empirical data, several key findings have emerged that highlight the crucial role of branding strategies in shaping consumer perceptions, preferences, and purchasing decisions.

Overall, this study provides strong evidence of the considerable influence of branding on consumer purchasing behaviour within the context of Ajmi food products. By understanding how branding influences consumer perceptions, preferences, and decisions, Ajmi can continue to refine its branding strategies to maintain a competitive advantage in the market. Ultimately, effective branding attracts customers, builds trust, enhances brand loyalty, and contributes to long-term business success.

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